

Factors Affecting Intention of Traveling Abroad of Vietnamese People

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Abstract:

This study has approached the nature of the relationship between the factors affecting the Vietnamese decision to travel abroad. From the theoretical basis of consumer behavior and overview of theories about buying decision-making behavior of customers, the author has identified the factors, identified the relationship model among the factors in the total. (internal factors of each individual: attitude, motivation; factors from the external environment, including: destination image, business approach to customers, influence of reference group). Inheriting the theory of planned behavioral action by Ajzen (1991), model research on travel decisions by Um and Crompton (1990); Woodside and MacDonald (1994); Decrop (2006b), the author initially establishes a theoretical model suitable to the research context of factors affecting the decision to travel abroad of Vietnamese people.

Keywords: Intention, traveling abroad, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In recent years, Vietnam has had strong changes in international integration. This change comes primarily from international cooperation activities and the increasingly improved role of Vietnam in the international arena. Vietnam's accession into multilateral institutions such as the United Nations (UN), Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC), the World Trade Organization (WTO) ... Not only in the economic field, in the guest fields such as politics, culture-society, security-defense, science and technology, education ... etc also have positive developments.

International cultural exchanges in the region and in the world have been promoted in breadth and depth with many rich and diversified activities. As a member of ASEAN, UNESCO ... Vietnam has played an important role in promoting cultural exchange activities for tourists coming and going. These are favorable conditions for the expansion of tourism business in general and foreign tourism business in particular.

The work of citizen protection and support for overseas Vietnamese has been promoted by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Measures to respond to crisis, natural disasters, fires, and accident assistance have been well implemented in the region and countries with Vietnamese diplomatic representatives. The legal system related to overseas Vietnamese has been focused on perfecting. The policy mechanism for business investment activities for overseas Vietnamese enterprises has also been improved towards more openness. As of 2018, there are about 3,000 Vietnamese enterprises investing abroad with a total capital of about 4 billion USD (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2019).

Visa regulations and immigration procedures are also simpler and more open to Vietnamese people. Currently, 51 countries exempt Vietnamese citizens from visa-free entry and stay for 14 to 30 days (Consular Department, 2020). Some countries simplify visa application procedures and remove previous barriers for Vietnamese citizens.

Resources for income and working conditions in recent years have also been enhanced. The statistics of the average income per capita of Vietnam in 2018 in urban and rural areas are above 200% compared to 2010. Conditions of living standards, social security, period The resting time in recent years has been markedly improved. That creates conditions for Vietnamese people to have more opportunities to participate in overseas tours.

2. Literature review

2.1. Overview of factors influencing travel decisions

The traveler buying behavior can be viewed from three theoretical perspectives, including: Decision making; experience; and behavioral influences (Mowen John, 1988). The decision-making stance holds that buying is the result of consumers participating in the problem-solving process - finding solutions to the problems they face. The empirical point of view argues that under certain circumstances, consumers make purchases to create feelings, experiences, and emotions rather than to solve problems. Behavioral influences suggest that in other cases the consumer acts in response to environmental stimuli or stresses.

In studies of travel decision making are referred to as the act of general consideration before making a general decision: Yes or No traveling (Raaij et al., 1984; Um and Crompton, 1990; Mansfeld, 1996) before specifying which aspects the traveler determines. Seddighi and Theocharous (2002) also argue that firstly, tourists are identified as facing a general decision to vacation or not. Second, prospective tourists have to choose between a domestic and foreign vacation, which is primarily determined by their affordability. Then, new customers develop awareness and emotion to choose their destination. These perceptions and emotions are considered the decisive criterion through an abstraction of the system's characteristics. Perceptions and emotions are aggregated into the priority order of the intended target choices that will lead to the final decision (this process is governed by situations like vacation availability). Third, the travel experience is to do a round trip to revise the perceptions and feelings of previously selected destinations.

In the research limit of the thesis will ignore the general decision (whether to go or not to travel) of the customer. Tourists' decision-making will be understood that they have decided to travel and that research focuses on which aspects to answer the research question are 'what aspects' that tourists choose when making decisions. intend to join a foreign tour. With that in mind, further research will look at a customer's decision based on a set of customer decisions. Um and Crompton (1990) introduce the concept of a "selection toolkit" and argue that customer perception goes through two stages. He hypothesized that the destination selection depends on attitudes towards a trip to that destination; and alternatives are filtered out from a list of individual customer ratings. Decrop (2006b) summarized and concluded that the decision variable and the content of the tourist's choice decision are closely related.

In addition, the concept of Tourism products used in the thesis is understood as a pre-scheduled foreign tour program and includes all transportation, accommodation, food and beverage services, and instructors. and other services included in the program (Sheldon and Mak, 1987). Thus, each package tour product will contain individual services that businesses put into their service packages, and these are also aspects that allow consumers to choose to suit their criteria. suggest. The options are presented in the following aspects: Schedule organized; Places to visit in the program; Hotel accommodation; Transportation; instructor; Trip length... etc. Each of these options is considered as subdecisions but has a reciprocal impact on a tourist's decision to purchase a package tour service.

Previous studies on factors influencing the decision to travel, abroad show that factors influencing a tourist's travel decision can be divided into main groups, including: Factors stemming from the individual psychology of tourists, including Attitude to tourism products, Tourism Motivation; The group of factors has an impact from the external environment to attract tourists such as Destination Image, Business approach to customers and the influence from Reference Group; and group of individual control factors (Actual Behavioral Control) of each individual.

Psychological factors in each individual: Some scholars also classify factors affecting tourism decisions by groups of push factors (push factor) and pull factor (pull factor). In the thesis, the thesis supports the classification of internal factors (factors derived from the inner psychology of each individual) and external (factors with attraction from the external environment have impact on psychology. consumers). In which:

Attitude: studies of general consumer attitudes (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Shimp, 1981) show that Attitudes and beliefs are the expression of human emotions about a product, whether the assessment can be good or bad, but they're all based on cognitive outcomes. Emotions and thereby create action trends when making buying decisions. While belief expresses affirmative thoughts that people get through knowledge or through public opinion. Other studies in tourism (Nichols and Snepenger, 1988; Um and Crompton, 1990; Cullingford, 1995; Crick, 2003; Feng et al., 2006; Phillips and Jang, 2008; Pietro et al, 2012; Levitt et al., 2019) also affirms that the attitude factor may or may not be influenced by emotional factors. For example, an image of a travel product or a travel business created by public trust will have a motivating effect on a customer's love / hate attitude when it comes to the product or business. From that attitude will have an influence on the intention to buy the product and the specific behavior of the tourist buying decision.

Although the attitude factor studies covered in the previous study are quite complete and clear. However, each study applies different contexts and data collected. For considering how the attitude factor affects the travel decision, it is necessary to put in a more comprehensive model, full of psychological factors in each individual, impact factors. Only awareness from the external environment can clarify the impact of these factors.

Motivation: Travel motivation mentioned in Dann (1977); Crompton (1979); Ross (1994); Murphy (2013). The motivation for deciding to choose a tourism product comes from needs at a level strong enough to motivate people to come to satisfy that need. Travel motivation is represented by two groups of push and pull factors (Dann, 1977; Kent, 1990; Gnoth, 1997; Gordon, 2004). Many researchers have developed the theory and clarification of motivations as important factors in the study of consumer decision-making in tourism (Crompton, 1979; Fodness, 1994; Ross, 1994; Gnoth, 1997). Decrop (2006b) argues that the motivations for choosing and buying travel lie in the following aspects: 1) Exiting from everyday life; 2) Discover something new; 3) Rest; 4) Seeking experience; 5) Seeking fun; 6) Asserting self-worth (Dann, 1977); and 7) Getting to the right place (MacCannell, 1973). In which:

1) Motivation to escape from everyday life: Mannell and Iso-Ahola (1987) have developed a psychological model of travel dynamics, in which search and escape goals are an important part of the cave. travel agency. Decrop (2006b, p.80) asserts that for the majority of tourists the purpose is to leave everyday life. Purpose to get rid of the stress associated with professional activities or the stress of family affairs is often the main driving force. Holiday activities will be a time for people to restore health and mental state.

2) Motivation to discover novelties: Crompton (1979) points out in his research that the motive from the need to discover new things (exploration) in tourism is one of the main. of tourists. Decrop (2006b) also added that the purpose of discovering new things and visiting a destination to gain understanding often attaches a well-defined goal: for example, to explore the lives of local people living as how, explore other cultures or go to historical sites ... This motive is often the opposite of relaxation and visitors often do not aim for profit first.

3) Motivation of rest: Rest and relaxation to remove stress are very basic needs of trips purpose. The purpose of rest is not only material enjoyment, but also people want to seek long-term benefits such as better mood, better work or recovery. Travel is like a therapy that creates the conditions necessary to let go of everyday problems while at the same time solving them through restoring a clear mind (Decrop, 2006b).

4) Experiences Seeker: Experience or experience is the only residue in the post-consumer phase of travel product consumption. From a personal perspective, the motivation to seek experience is to increase understanding, awareness or simply to respond to the discovery curiosity of the things that individual experiences during the travel journey. From a collective perspective, the need to seek out a companion experience stems from the need to interact positively outside of the everyday environment (Dann, 1977; Decrop, 2006b). Recent studies show that visitors' need to seek out experiences and sharing is not only at the individual or companion level, but also with non-companions through social networks (Pietro and partners, 2012; Singh and Srivastava, 2019).

5) The motivation for pleasure: comes from the reality of the need to do interesting and playful activities in order to have a better life and forget about everything in just a few days. The main purpose of travel is for fun and fun related to recreational activities, sports, social networking or romantic experiences. This motive is often found in younger generation travelers, family members or groups (Crompton, 1979; Gnoth, 1997; Jang and Cai, 2002).

6) The motivation to assert self-worth: attached to cultural factors has long been considered as the factor affecting the buying decision of consumers. Naturally, every person living in a cultural environment will be influenced by learning the perceived aspects of value, ideas, and understanding of the meaning of each member of that society (Blackwell et al. the, 2001). McCracken (2005) argues that culture includes the way in which beliefs, values, norms and non-standard behaviors, consumption habits ... influence consumer behavior in tourism. Social class is usually divided based on factors such as income, wealth, education, occupation or other criteria. Individuals belonging to the same social class often show a preference for similar cognitive values and attitudes. Each individual living in a different cultural environment and social strata has the need to assert their own values differently. And this is also the motivation of tourists to join the tours.

7) Motivation to get to the right place you want: MacCannell (1973) thinks that the true purpose of getting to the right place to have the authentic experience is the motivation that motivates visitors to travel itineraries. According to Gnoth (1997), the images (celebrities, idolized role models), places or spaces provided on the film are attractive suggestions that urge tourists to take part in itineraries. calendar to where that suggestion is.

Factors from the external environment: most of the research on factors affecting travel decisions mentioned about attraction, attracting tourists is destination image, impact from activities. business approaches and opinions from reference groups. Inside:

Destination image: Reflects the perceptions of travelers thinking about the destination. Destination awareness may be caused by external stimulating information such as a destination's cultural characteristics, natural resources, or other attractiveness, which is received by visitors from a variety of sources. Destination perception has three basic levels of perception, attention, and interpretation of information. Gordon (2004) explains that destination perception is the process of information processing in the human brain that goes through the steps of receiving information, processing and evaluating, accepting and storing information in memory. Thus, personal experience accumulated from previous trips will be the basis for comparison and evaluation for future trips and thus it directly affects attitudes and motivations. with the travel product and indirectly influences the tourist's decisions. The destination image is composed of basic factors such as natural resources, historical and cultural values, customs, destination conditions such as other environments such as geography, political stability and Technical and scientific factors also directly or indirectly influence consumer decision-making in tourism (Hyde, 2004; McCracken, 2005; Swarbrooke and Horner, 2007).

Although the destination image has been studied quite fully by many of the above authors, but the above studies aim to explain the decision-making behavior of choosing a destination instead of choosing a product. Package tour. In the decision to choose a package tour, the destination image is only one of the constituent factors of a tourism product. This shows the need to place the destination image factor in the more general and complete theoretical model. Therefore, the destination image is mentioned in the thesis as one of the attractive factors from the environment affecting tourism attitudes and motivation.

Business approach to customers is one of the two most important factors affecting tourism destination selection behavior (Woodside and Lysonski, 1989). Woodside and MacDonald (1994) in the interpretive model also argued that marketing factors have an impact on the process of receiving information, evaluating and selecting information before making travel intentions. It includes advice from a travel agent; advertising on the media; direct mailing, especially through tour guides; tourism fair ... etc. Kotler (2017) affirms that the price and quality of services included in the tour are the two most important factors in the group of marketing factors that affect the decision-making of tourists. In addition, promotions are also factors that directly and indirectly affect

consumer decision-making in tourism. From a review of previous studies (Mayo and Jarvis, 1981; Crick, 2003; Gruen, 2005; Middleton et al., 2009; Luo and Zhong, 2015) on tourism marketing and the relationship of the influencing factors. the decision-making process, the dissertation and the use of the concept of customer access are the factors that represent the group of marketing factors in the proposed model.

The above studies on customer outreach activities only put this factor in the overall marketing activities of the business. The objective of these studies is to evaluate the nature of marketing activities to the decision to choose tourism products. The majority of these studies do not place customer outreach activities in relation to external stimuli such as destination images, reference groups ... In addition, lack of viewing A travel decision review is merely a buyer's decision that leads to unidirectional or purely economic explanation of decision-making. In fact, travel decisions need to be considered in many aspects of psychology, experience, perception ...

Reference group: contains references from family members, or social groups, in which:

1) Family is the most important purchasing and consuming unit, so many scholars are interested in doing research. Consumer decision-making in tourism with spousal or both decision-making has been studied for many years (Jenkins, 1978; Filiatrault and Ritchie, 1980; Nichols and Snepenger, 1988; Fodness, 1992 ; Decrop, 2006b). There is also a strong influence of children in parental decision-making when consuming tourism products (Howard and Madrigal, 1990; Cullingford, 1995).

2) Social group: every individual making decision for his or her trip is considered by the influence of the reference group in society (Gitelson and Kerstetter, 1995). Reference groups can influence the purpose of the trip (eg visiting friends, visiting family members, etc.) but can also influence in terms of group participation in first, during, and after making a decision. In addition, each individual is considered in terms of a certain role and position in society. Each different social position will affect the perception and behavior of that person when making consumption decisions.

One of the powerful influences on the decision to travel is word of mouth (WOM). Arndt (1967) pioneered research on the influence of word of mouth in consumer decision-making. In the tourism sector, there are many studies showing different degrees of the influence of information on attitudes (beliefs), motivating customers to choose to buy tourism products (Moital, 2006; Pan et al., 2007). The essence of word of mouth is the process by which a consumer experiences a certain product or service and passes it on (both positive and negative) to others for non-commercial purposes. Word of mouth is considered more trustworthy and more trustworthy than other forms of corporate control such as corporate marketing communications, advertising and promotion (Breazeale, 2009; Dye, 2000). A key feature of word of mouth is interpersonal communication; information related to the product or service that has been experienced; the communicator's purpose is non-profit.

In recent years, with the explosion of global information networks and especially the popularity of social networks, there has been an electronic form of word of mouth (eWOM - Electronic Word-Of-Mouth) based on media and internet. Over the past decade, more and more research has been directed towards understanding the effectiveness of eWOM and its effect on consumer behavior (Murphy et al., 2007). Some researchers approach eWOM as whether the positive or negative information presented has an impact on potential consumers about a product or the business that offers that product (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004). Some other researchers Litvin et al (2008); Phelan et al (2013) argued that the main concept of the eWOM studied was related not only to perceptions of the usefulness of references but also to attitudes toward using social media as a Effective communication channel for tourist destination selection. This research approach focuses on the role factor of the social network provides and shows there is a basis for a stronger predictor of consumer attitudes when making product choice decisions.

The difference between WOM and eWOM is the communication method, the information limitation and the relationship between the actors participating in the communication process. eWOM uses information dissemination methods based on social media instead of direct communication. Thus, information from an

individual can be communicated quickly to many people (Black and Kelley, 2009). Information published on the internet can exist for a long time and can be accessed on a global scale (Cheung et al., 2008). There are still many different views on the concept of eWOM, but most authors emphasize the important influence of eWOM in the client's decision-making process.

Control variables: including factors reflecting personal characteristics including age, family status, education and occupation, personality and lifestyle ... Factors are assessed as having a direct impact on the tourism motivation and travel decisions of consumers (Decrop, 2000). Determination of travel characteristics such as trip length, trip distance, means of transport ... is also selected differently at different ages. Marital status (single, young couple, nuclear family, multi-generational family ...) directly affects criteria for product selection and decision-making, and is a premise for factors in the secondary group. Family life cycle is a combination of age and family status considered by researchers to distinguish tourist groups (Gitelson and Kerstetter, 1990). The important factors in the control variable include:

Education and career attainment are factors that indirectly influence the decision-making and sub-decisions of tourists. Education level is considered in terms of the basic knowledge that consumers accumulate. Knowledge is one of the factors mentioned as one of the psychological factors affecting consumer decision-making. Knowledge is closely related to perception. The information that people perceive will help develop one's knowledge and skills and in this way help people respond in similar circumstances in the future. Knowledge will help people connect information stored in memory with new information to come up with the most suitable answer. For example, when choosing a tourist destination, tourists are often related to previously acquired knowledge such as climate, natural conditions, culture ... where they are expected to go to choose the right place for them. . In addition, each person's occupation also affects their own service consumption conditions. So careers will create distinct characteristics of income, time funds and other conditions in consumer purchasing decisions.

Personality is a characteristic psychological trait of each person that affects his or her behavior toward environmental stimuli. The psychological characteristics that make up a personality are often confident, active, sociable, independent, etc. (Mayo and Jarvis, 1981). Personality is considered to be a useful variable when analyzing consumer behavior through personality type classification. Each personality type is strongly correlated with an associated product or service preference (Plog, 2001). Attached to the concept of personality is self-awareness (self-concept). Including 2 aspects are the image that people think about themselves and how the image they pursue to achieve (eg ideal type, character image ... etc) (Grubb and Stern, 1971).

Lifestyle is the self-manifestation of a person's own characteristics reflected in his or her activities, interests or attitudes. Each individual belongs to the same social class or cultural group but may have different lifestyles, contained in the lifestyle are characteristics that are unique to that person. Plog (2001) identifies 8 lifestyle types of tourists, including adventurous tourists, pleasure-seeking, impulsive, self-confident, always planning, masculine, intellectual and others-oriented . Mayo and Jarvis (1981) or Mazanec et al (1994) also identified many different tourist lifestyles. Lifestyle is seen as a structural and sustainable factor in each individual that has a significant impact on the tourist's buying decision-making process.

Income: Decrop (2000) argues that an individual's income status, which strongly depends on age, family and profession, has a direct influence on the decision to join the trip, may be explained by two mental states: 1) the urge to travel despite economic benefits; and 2) Obstruction to travel due to an income barrier. Thus, income is the most basic condition to make the trip. But it is also the driving factor that motivates travel in economic terms. In addition, income will also be a barrier to travel decisions, or affect the adjustment of decisions about itinerary, time, and price of a trip.

2.2. Overview of studies on the decision to travel abroad

In recent years, there have been more in-depth studies on the subject of decision-making behavior to travel abroad. It can be seen that studies on this topic have attracted the attention of many researchers in all continents. In Asia, researches focus mainly on countries with large growth in foreign tourist markets such as China, Japan, Korea, Taiwan (Nozawa, 1992; Chen, 2001; Chang, 2009; Sparks and Pan, 2009; Lee et al., 2012). Chang (2009) identifies the specific aspects of services such as quality, reliability, responsiveness, empathy and tangibility and considers them the most fundamental factors that influence intent. option for a Taiwanese foreign tour. The research results of (Nozawa, 1992) show that it is easier for Japanese to make decisions based on the quality of service and safety of the destination. Factors that can greatly affect customers' choice are advertising and marketing, attractiveness from destination shopping, and hindering foreign language usage. In countries with European culture, research by Jang and Cai (2002); Bryce (2007); Dogru and Sirakaya-Turk (2018); Pappas (2019); Balli et al (2019) show a more complete picture of the relationship between the factors influencing the decision to travel abroad by local people in one aspect or another.

Although there is a closer approach to aspects of the research topic on travel decisions, it is easy to see that these studies come from the context of the study of foreign travel market countries. has evolved for a long time. Consumption habits in the cultures mentioned in these studies still have many differences compared to Vietnamese. The general demographic conditions such as income, standard of living and lifestyle of tourists are also different when compared to Vietnamese. Therefore, theories about the relationship between the factors affecting consumer behavior of tourists should be placed in the context of specific research in Vietnam.

Factors affecting from the environment to the decision to travel abroad have been updated in many recent studies. Research on destination image factors and the impact on tourists' decision when choosing foreign tours such as Guillet et al (2011); Andreu et al (2014); Li et al (2017). The results of these studies show that destination image is confirmed to be the most basic factor affecting customers' decision to buy tours. Guillet et al (2011) provided some important findings when researching overseas tourists in Hong Kong and pointed out that trip cost, length of stay in trip, size of tourist group are important factors that directly affect your choice of destination. Andreu et al. (2014) pointed out that cultural distance, diversity of heritage, the existence of an expat community or a willingness to connect in flight are important, constituent, and photographic factors. affect the decision of tourists to travel abroad. However, there is a difference between the destination image in perception of the customer at the first time and subsequent visits to a country. Besides, the image of the destination is also different between groups that participate in tours with different purposes and types.

One of the factors considered "pull" factor, which has a strong impact on the attitude and motivation of customers to travel abroad is advertising activities, approaching from enterprises. Andreu et al (2014) point out that the impact of promotion on culture, not only heritage but also traditions of each destination, festivals, customs, cuisine, etc., has a strong impact. in attracting customers to foreign tours. Travel businesses also rely on the diversity of information distribution channels to increase efficiency and reach customers.

Influencing factors Reference groups, associated with the growing popularity of the internet and social media, are also mentioned in recent studies, contributing to enriching theories explaining tourist behavior foreign calendar. Singh and Srivastava (2019) report that social media and internet communication not only impact perceptions within individuals, but it also creates a tendency to link individuals together on a more frequent basis. Tourists increasingly rely on other people's opinions as they join the online community. Tourists are also influenced by opinions of individuals with a large social network, which tend to be more connected and engaged in social media environments. Pietro et al (2012); Munar and Jacobsen (2014) provide scientific evidence on the impact of social media on tourism motivation, attitudes and intention to choose foreign tours. In it, Pietro et al. (2012) contributed theoretically important to understanding regarding the use of social networks for tourism destinations and marketing purposes. The authors model the key influence variables for travelers and how users are affected. The findings focused specifically on the role of electronic word of mouth (eWOM) enjoyment and communication in both consumer attitudes and intentions.

One of the new approaches when studying foreign travel decision-making behavior is to study the change in perceptions of consumer generations. Gardiner et al. (2013) refer to the differences in the factors that influence travel decisions between generations in terms of travel experience, search and participation in North American tourists. Typical of the difference between the silent generation (Silent Generation - the older generation) and the younger generation (Boomer) relates to tourism motivation as well as tourism activities. While younger generations seek more energetic experiences like physical excitement, adventure and longer family time, older people pursue calmer experiences like casinos and food, history and culture. Research results by Huang and Lu (2017) show that there is a significant difference between the five generations when making a decision to travel abroad by Chinese people. In particular, the difference comes from tourism motives, information search and information sources, destination evaluation criteria.

The main difference between the consumption habits of Asian foreign tourists versus European cultural regions is that Asians have a preference for signing up for package tours in large groups. Most recent studies of Asian consumption characteristics and habits have mentioned this characteristic (Nozawa, 1992; Huang et al., 1996; Prideaux, 1997; Lee et al., 2012; Chen and partner, 2019). Lee et al. (2012) generalized from their research findings that the size and power of the outbound tourism spending in Asia is increasing. In addition to the reasons of price, convenience, and psychological enjoyment of tourists. This study also shows that language barrier is also one of the reasons driving Asian tourists' sentiment in groups and choosing package tours as their number one priority. In addition, risk perception is also one of the factors that contribute to this trait among Asian tourists (Hsu and Lin, 2014).

In general, these studies have mentioned in a deeper perspective the impact of the tourist destination factor on tourist purchasing decisions. However, only focus on one or some basic factors such as destination image, marketing activities, reference group ... etc. While other factors have not been included to create a more general, more comprehensive model to approach to travel decision-making behavior, which is considered very complex.

3. Research Methods

The research methods used in the thesis are a combination of qualitative research methods and quantitative research methods. The reason for the combination of the two research methods is because of the specific characteristics of the research context and characteristics of the consumption culture of Vietnamese tourists. The study is in the socio-cultural and tourism market context of the Vietnamese people, so there is no similarity with the context in previous studies in Western countries. Therefore, it is necessary to use qualitative research methods to analyze the initial discovery, evaluate the suitability of the model, and adjust the scale of variables in quantitative research for the research context in Vietnam. Qualitative research was carried out by in-depth interviews with 7 tourism experts and sample in-depth interviews with 10 Vietnamese tourists.

Quantitative research is used in the thesis to test theoretical models, the relationships between the elements in the theoretical model and the mentioned research hypotheses. Data collected from questionnaires were distributed to Vietnamese tourists in airport lounges prior to their overseas tour. Research results are based on the results of analyzing the reliability of the scale Cronbach's Alpha, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmation factor analysis (CFA) and linear structural model analysis.

Research models

The model proposed above on the one hand ensures the structural design of the rational behavioral theory model to explain the tourist's decision-making behavior. The inheritance model is structured relationships that explain the behavior of planned behavioral theory, but at the same time it adds specific elements that explain tourist behavior.

Basic elements inherited from Planning Behavioral Theory include:

- 1) Attitude toward foreign tourism (Attitude toward the Behavior).
- 2) Travel motor (Perceived Behavioral Control)

The model inherits the factors that influence travel decisions from research in the tourism field. These factors are placed in order to reflect the impact from environmental factors to individual psychological factors, including:

- 1) Destination image: Inherited from Um and Crompton (1990) represents the factors that create the attraction from the outside that affects the psychology and perception of each individual.
- 2) Customer outreach activities: mentioned in the model of Woodside and MacDonald (1994), representing the pull factor from the marketing activities of the business.
- 3) Reference group: inherited from Decrop (2006b); (Woodside and MacDonald, 1994), demonstrating influences from the environment to the subjective standard perception of each individual.

4. Result

Based on the analysis of the Eigenvalue value from the initial value until the stop (Eigenvalues value > 1 and the cumulative percentage of the total square of the extracted factor load factor > 50%). With such conditions, the analytical results shown in the table above show that there are 6 factors with Eigenvalues value in the last factor reaching 1,671 (> 1) and the cumulative percentage reaches 65,886% (> 50%).). Based on the above analysis results from SPSS software, it is possible to confirm that the factors with distinct values meet the requirements set out in Chapter 3. After analyzing the discriminant value, the author proceeds to analyze. The converged value through the data analysis results shown in the table below

Table 1. Pattern Matrix after normalization

	Factors					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
DES1			0,873			
DES2			0,881			
DES3			0,775			
DES4			0,904			
DES5			0,890			
ADS1					0,898	
ADS2					0,886	
ADS3					0,878	
ADS5					0,853	
SOC1				0,695		
SOC2				0,915		
SOC3				0,838		
SOC4				0,864		
SOC5				0,774		
ATT1						0,746
ATT2						0,753
ATT3						0,709
ATT4						0,664
DIS2	0,549					
DIS3	0,698					
DIS4	0,687					
DIS5	0,691					
SHA2	0,638					
SHA3	0,726					
SHA4	0,745					
FIN1	0,820					
FIN2	0,860					
FIN3	0,882					
FIN4	0,893					
SEL1	0,849					
SEL2	0,860					
SEL4	0,857					
DEC1		0,790				
DEC3		0,794				
DEC4		0,773				
DEC5		0,803				
DEC7		0,769				
DEC8		0,776				
DEC10		0,806				
DEC11		0,786				
DEC12		0,824				
DEC13		0,831				

Table 2. Results of convergence value analysis and differentiation in CFA

	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV	ATT	DEC	DES	SOC	ADS	MOT
ATT	0,815	0,524	0,189	0,135	0,724					
DEC	0,945	0,634	0,163	0,107	0,404	0,796				
DES	0,939	0,754	0,312	0,144	0,299	0,294	0,869			
SOC	0,920	0,697	0,268	0,160	0,337	0,244	0,358	0,835		
ADS	0,936	0,785	0,312	0,180	0,343	0,275	0,559	0,481	0,886	
MOT	0,949	0,822	0,268	0,176	0,435	0,390	0,322	0,518	0,406	0,907

The CFA analysis results presented above show that there is a basis to conclude that the factors used in this study achieve reliability (measured by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, synthetic reliability - CR), convergence (measured by the extracted mean variance coefficient - AVE), achieving discriminant values (measured by the largest individual variance coefficient - MSV; Square root of the extracted mean variance SQRTAVE).

These factors continue to be used in the testing steps with the linear structure model - SEM in the next step.

Table 3. Estimated results, tested by Bootstrap, n = 1,000

Relationship	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE_Bias	C.R=Bias/SE_Bias
ATT <--- DES	0,054	0,001	0,141	0,004	0,002	2
ATT <--- SOC	0,05	0,001	0,217	0,003	0,002	1,5
ATT <--- ADS	0,05	0,001	0,166	-0,006	0,002	-3
MOT <--- ADS	0,046	0,001	0,159	-0,004	0,002	-2
MOT <--- SOC	0,041	0,001	0,41	-0,002	0,001	-2
MOT <--- DES	0,047	0,001	0,092	0,003	0,002	1,5
FIN <--- MOT	0,046	0,001	0,893	0,001	0,002	0,5
SEL <--- MOT	0,044	0,001	0,876	0,001	0,002	0,5
SHA <--- MOT	0,052	0,001	0,904	0,001	0,002	0,5
DIS <--- MOT	0,019	0	0,954	-0,001	0,001	-1
DEC <--- MOT	0,047	0,001	0,274	-0,005	0,002	-2,5
DEC <--- ATT	0,047	0,001	0,304	0,002	0,002	1

The above Bootstrap analysis results table shows the difference (bias column) between the estimate value and the mean value column with very small absolute value and small C.R critical value. More than or equal to 2 at all the estimated coefficients, so a very small deviation between the estimated result and the mean result at 800 times estimated from the random sample can be considered, so at 95% confidence of the result. Results estimated from the initial model and from the mean of the other 800 estimates give the same or reliable results.

5. Conclusion

The research results have identified new factors, explaining the trend of the decision to choose a tour in the current context has a huge impact on the factors of information sources. word of mouth (WOM) and especially electronic word of mouth (eWOM). The growth of social networks incessantly over the years has made a quite clear change in the mechanism of interaction between factors on the decision to choose tourism products of customers today. Specifically in this case, it is a Vietnamese decision to travel abroad.

Quantitative analysis with analytical results Cronbach's Alpha helps confirm the reliability of the scale of factors in the research model. Using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient with the minimum acceptance level > 0.6 and the total variable correlation coefficient > 0.3 as a basis for determining the reliability of the scale of the factors. Factor evaluation results Destination image with 0.938 is rated as satisfactory in terms of reliability. No observed variables are removed. Variables Outreach activities have Cronbach's Alpha coefficient reached 0.915. However, one variable (ADS6) was rejected due to the unsatisfactory total variable correlation coefficient (0.14) and was therefore excluded from the scale. Cronbach's Alpha analysis of factors The reference groups give results 0.917 and observed variables have total variable correlation coefficients > 0.3 meet the requirements. So this factor scale is accepted. Similar analysis results show that the variable scale of Attitude towards foreign tourism reaches the necessary confidence level. Scale of factors Travel motivation is analyzed by reliability analysis method of factor 2, which includes Tier 1 factors which are constituent factors Tourism motivation is: Discover new points, gather new knowledge, and experience; Share your experiences and

experiences with others; Seek fun; Find and assert yourself. After excluding the observed variables with the total variable correlation coefficient <0.3 , these factors have Cronbach's Alpha coefficients respectively 0.861; 0.843; 0.922 and 0.933 are satisfactory. The remaining observed variables are accepted for analysis in the next step. For the scale of the decision to travel, after eliminating some observed variables, the total variable correlation coefficient is unsatisfactory, the results remain 11 observed variables. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the variable Decision to travel reached 0.941 and is accepted.

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